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TEACHING ECONOMIC TERMS TO ESP STUDENTS

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Annotation: *This article considers key aspects associated with teaching English terminology in economic discourse and establishes interconnections binding the generic and specific ESP components. The topic appears relevant, because lack of expertise in the field of terminology precludes a student from getting an insight into the economic activities and hinders intercultural business communication.*

Key words: *economic, lexical phraseological termin, terminology, student, teacher, translation, encyclopediac, technique.*

ESP training of future economic experts is a specific process that primarily involves the study of lexical and phraseological units and the features of their functioning, since a professional jargon is often viewed as a terminology system. Terminology study evidently relies upon the use of translation dictionaries, thesaurus dictionaries and encyclopedias. The teaching techniques applied to introduce terminology draw upon various approaches, among which the definitional and the cognitive (epistemological) approaches are to be highlighted. The latter feeds upon the unity of word and concept, the language and the thought, linguistic and extra-linguistic factors affecting the development of terminology, as well as the semantics of individual terms. It has been discovered that elements of terminology system tend to migrate from one jargon to another within various professional subcultures. At that, the same concept may be perceived differently by representatives of different cultures. Furthermore, studying professional jargons helps establish a relationship binding the generic and the specific in the structure of the occupational language. Various integration models giving evidence of the hierarchical coordination of terms (thesauruses, terminology sets, denotation maps) should be subject to extensive application when teaching terminology.

In all the works devoted to terminology, the units that represent certain concepts of one or another field and mainly perform the nominative function are considered to be terms. Currently, the growth of the issue of terminology, on the one hand, is seen as the increase of new concepts due to the dynamic development of science, agriculture, and economy, and on the other hand, it is explained by the need for a deeper study of issues such as the development and function of terms.

There are many effective methods in economics, but some of them are the most used.

Cost-Benefit Analysis (Xarajat-foйда tahlili): A method used to evaluate the costs and benefits associated with a particular decision or policy.

Supply and Demand Analysis (Talab va taklif tahlili): A key concept in economics used to understand how a market works by studying the relationship between buyers and sellers.

Regression Analysis (Regressiya tahlili): A statistical technique used to determine the relationship between two or more variables.

Game Theory (O'yin nazariyasi): An approach used to analyze decision making in complex situations where the outcome of one person's decision depends on the decisions of others

Experimental economics (Eksperimental iqtisodiyot:): A method used to test economic theories by conducting controlled experiments in a laboratory setting.

A term is a nominative word or word combination (a noun or a word combination with a noun as a basically neutral word (combination of words) that belongs to a certain field of science and technology and is used by experts in this field, expressing the specificity of an object or concept. The terminological lexicon helps to define the content of the subject in a more comprehensible, accurate, and comprehensive manner. In special literature, terms are semantically distinguished from other literary lexicon. Nomen are names of single things. At the same time, it also serves to name mass products that are developed individually. The difference between nouns and terms is that they represent only single concepts, while terms represent general concepts. Preterms are social lexemes that are used as terms to name newly formed concepts. Examples of preterms include:

a) a descriptive phrase is a multi-word nominative phrase that clearly describes the concept, but does not meet the requirement of brevity;

b) connected phrase;

c) adjective or adverbial phrase;

Demand and supply, the concept that the price and quantity of goods and services in a free market is determined by the existence of demand and supply for this product. Opportunity cost is the cost of an alternative that must be given up in order to take a particular action or decision. Inflation is the rate of increase over time in the overall prices of goods and services in an economy. Gross domestic product is the total value of all goods and services produced in a country over a period of time. Monetary policy is the process by which the government controls the supply and demand of money in the economy. Fiscal policy, the use of government spending and taxes to influence the economy. Market structure: level of competition and monopoly power in a given market. These are just a few of the many economic terms that are important for students to learn. When teaching these concepts, it's important to break them down into

simple language and use real-life examples to help students understand their practical applications.

In economic terminology, it can be seen that the terms of this field are formed with the participation of the following affixes.

1. The suffix which is very active in the English language, primarily forms personal names of various categories. In the economic terminological system, he creates many terms meaning a person working in a certain field of the economy: economist, treasurer, sorter, tenant, consumer, taxman, provider, contractor, industrialist, supervisor, financier, depositor, competitor, customer, guarantor, etc.

2. The affix forms lexemes with different meanings in the English language.

The fact that some of them are somewhat active in terminological systems can be seen in the example of a number of scientific works. With the help of this affix, although in a small amount, some economic terms were made, the following examples can confirm our opinion: ghamlama, ustama, association, association, structure, order, division, collection, etc.

3. With the presence of the affix: This affix forms the noun of a person engaged in the cultivation of an object-object (such as a farmer, grain farmer), in the economic terminological system it is added to abstract nouns, and a person engaged in the activity understood from them. makes a horse: quartermaster, entrepreneur, saver, entrepreneur, etc.

Economic education in the conditions of a developing market economy implies the use of modern pedagogical technologies, widely reflects the recognition of the importance of economic knowledge for the formation of practical skills of students. The effectiveness of teaching economic subjects is largely determined by the teaching methodology of a particular subject. In modern educational conditions, the role and importance of methodology in the field of economic sciences is constantly increasing. Economic education responds to changes in social development. Therefore, the problem of improving the methodology of teaching economics and other economic sciences becomes very urgent.

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